

CCG WORKING PAPER

THE CLIMATE–LAND– ENERGY–WATER NEXUS IN ZAMBIA: AN ASSESSMENT OF RESEARCH AND POLICY PRIORITIES

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CONTENTS

Key Messages.....	2
1 Introduction	3
2 Method	4
3 Nexus issues in Zambia	5
3.1 Overview of nexus issues	5
3.2 Water–Energy (Hydropower)	7
3.3 Water–Energy (Other).....	8
3.4 Land–Water–Energy (Irrigation).....	9
3.5 Land–Water–Energy (Irrigation & hydropower).....	10
3.6 Land–Water (Other)	11
3.7 Land–Energy.....	12
3.8 Whole nexus	14
4 How Zambian policy addresses nexus issues.....	14
4.1 Policy coherence.....	14
4.2 Policy gaps.....	16
4.3 Implementation	17
5 Recommendations	20
5.1 Research priorities	20
5.2 Policy recommendations.....	21
5.3 Summary.....	25
Annexes	25
References.....	25
Acknowledgements	31
Recommended citation.....	31

Key Messages

- With increasing climate impacts, there is a critical need to improve understanding of the interlinkages between climate, land, energy, and water (CLEWs) systems in Zambia. Co-ordinated management of these interconnected systems (known as the “CLEWs nexus”) is essential to address potential trade-offs and build resilience.
- Research has focused largely on a sub-set of nexus elements, namely: the vulnerability of hydropower generation to climate change impacts (particularly in the Zambezi River basin); current and future irrigation potential; some consideration of competing water demands; impacts of land-use practices on water resources; and impacts of charcoal production on forests. Key uncertainties remain around all these topics and their combined effects.
- Recent policy developments show an increasing recognition of CLEWs nexus issues. However, integrated analysis and management frameworks are yet to be well developed.
- Based on the existing research, it is recommended to prioritise diversified energy sources and efficient irrigation technologies, in order to support increased reliability and productivity in the energy and agriculture systems.
- Stronger reflection of several nexus issues is needed in various policies. Furthermore, strengthening coherence between sectoral policies in order to facilitate integrated solutions is vital for achieving long-term development goals.
- Regarding implementation, better alignment is needed between policy goals, strategies, and legal instruments, such as acts of parliament. Further policy recommendations are inspired by lessons learned from the international ‘Nexus Regional Dialogues Programme’.
- To facilitate improved resource management and policy coherence in Zambia, further nexus research is needed, prioritising elements including land implications of alternative energy sources, the potential and best ways to increase irrigation and manage competing energy resources, diversification of the energy system to ensure reliable future supply, and how economic and societal drivers exacerbate climate change vulnerabilities within Zambia.

1 Introduction

In Zambia, many key environmental, development, and economic challenges require strategies which consider multiple systems. Questions such as how best to manage water resources to facilitate increased reliability or expansion of hydropower along with water demands for irrigation, domestic, and industrial uses are becoming increasingly urgent as the impacts of climate change worsen.

Zambia is already experiencing the tangible effects of climate change, with changes in rainfall patterns, temperature fluctuations, and extreme weather events. These are exacerbating the vulnerabilities of Zambia’s interconnected land, water, and energy systems. Increased frequency and intensity of droughts, particularly in the southern and western regions, have led to reduced agricultural productivity and enormous challenges for hydropower generation (Lusaka Times, 2024). Changes in river flow patterns, particularly in the Zambezi but also in the Kafue River basins, have disrupted both hydropower reliability and water availability for irrigation and domestic use. Conversely, more frequent flooding events in the south and central regions have caused widespread displacement, destruction of infrastructure, and water contamination (eg IFRC, 2023).

These trends underscore the urgency of adopting integrated approaches to manage Zambia’s natural resources effectively. To address Zambia’s interconnected development and environmental challenges, improved understanding of the interlinkages between the so-called nexus of land, energy, and water systems is needed, along with research into integrated policy approaches that can mitigate conflicts over these vital resources. To this end, nexus approaches “use systems-based thinking to frame management options for the present and future”, thereby improving planning and regulatory decision-making across, in this case, the three sectors (Gomo et al., 2018, p.15).

A notable example of the successful application of a nexus approach in Southern Africa is the Southern African Development Community (SADC)’s Nexus Dialogue Project, which established a regional water–energy–food (WEF) nexus governance framework, a screening and appraisal tool for WEF nexus projects, and a prioritised list of nexus projects (Kabeya et al., 2022). By integrating the planning of water use for agriculture, hydropower, and other applications across sectors and national borders, these efforts help balance competing demands while fostering regional cooperation (Adelphi, 2023; Nhamo et al., 2018).

This working paper provides a review of the current literature relating to the climate–land–energy–water nexus in Zambia and assesses whether and how such issues are being considered in national strategies and policies. The insights gained through these reviews and a stakeholder workshop have helped identify a set of research priorities for future

work. By aiming to bridge knowledge gaps among policymakers, researchers, and practitioners, the paper contributes to fostering integrated approaches to Zambia's interconnected challenges.

Specifically, this working paper addresses the following Research Questions:

1. What are the most important nexus issues in Zambia, and how are they expected to evolve in the future due to human and environmental drivers?
2. What are the current gaps in Zambia's policy frameworks regarding nexus issues, and how could greater coherence across sectors enhance their effectiveness?
3. Which topics require further research, and what types of research should be prioritised?

The work was part of the Zambia Energy Resource Nexus project (ZERN), under the Climate Compatible Growth programme (CCG).

2 Method

An initial participatory exercise to map important links between the climate, land, energy, and water nexus elements was undertaken in February 2024 at the CCG Annual Workshop in Lusaka. Approximately 18 participants of the CCG Land-use Special Interest Group, representing government, NGOs, civil society and academia, identified links that are particularly relevant in Zambia, and discussed their dynamics.

This mapping informed the scope of a semi-structured literature review. This was conducted to assess the scope and depth of academic studies on the nexus topics identified, to address Research Question 1. Journal articles and reports were selected if they detailed studies examining one or more nexus links in Zambia, at regional, national, or sub-national scale. For each study, key details were recorded, including the research questions, the nexus links which were examined, how climate change was considered (eg GHG emissions or climate impacts), the degree of focus on technical, environmental, or policy analysis, methods, and findings. Key themes and gaps were identified. Recommendations were drawn from the literature – some of which also offered evidence-based strategies for addressing the challenges identified – and workshop discussions. Section 3 summarises the key insights from the review, and the emerging recommendations.

To address Research Question 2, a set of national policy documents relevant to climate, land, energy, and water (CLEWs) were identified for review. The method involved identification of the associated sector/ministries, a review of core objectives/aspirations

in each policy, and analysis of the extent of CLEWs integration (see Section 4). This was combined with findings from the literature review in order to identify gaps in both sectoral and cross-sectoral policy documents.

Finally, to inform Research Question 3, initial findings from the literature and policy reviews were discussed at a stakeholder workshop in Lusaka in November 2024. Bringing together approximately 25 participants from government, industry, civil society, and academia, discussions helped further develop an understanding of key nexus issues, research gaps and priorities, policy developments, and implementation challenges. Key recommendations are put forward in Section 5 of this report.

3 Nexus issues in Zambia

3.1 Overview of nexus issues

The links between the climate, land, energy, and water systems in Zambia, as highlighted by stakeholders in February 2024, are illustrated in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: CLEWs nexus links in Zambia (based on an unpublished diagram by Francesco Gardumi, KTH)

The following sections present the review of literature that examines elements of these nexus links. Most studies focus on just one or two elements. Drawing on that literature

and workshop discussions, **Figures 2 and 3** use scenarios to illustrate how multiple systems could be linked in a chain of impacts. These show the importance of mapping and quantifying the multiple interlinkages between climate, land, energy and water.

In the first scenario (**Figure 2**), population growth and increased electrification drive increased energy demands. Additional electricity generation capacity is built. If this is dominated by hydropower it is vulnerable to the increasing frequency and severity of droughts driven by climate change. (Note, outages could also be caused by damage to hydropower stations due to floods.) In a particular year, a drought causes a substantial reduction in hydropower generation. In response to load shedding, communities with electricity access switch from cooking with electricity to charcoal, and biomass use increases for industrial heat generation. Increased demand for biomass drives increased forest degradation and deforestation, particularly in areas close to urban centres, which leads to loss of biodiversity, increased water run-off, and soil degradation. In the following years, this places increasing pressure on agricultural land and food production.

Figure 2: Illustration of nexus links – Scenario 1

In the second scenario (**Figure 3**), the competition for water resources is also key. In the face of decreasing and more erratic rainfall, increasing irrigation is relied upon for maintaining and increasing crop yields. However, the competition for water with hydropower, industry and domestic use means the potential for irrigation is limited in some areas. If this limits the potential to increase yields, then agricultural land is likely to increase to meet growing demands for food and other commodities. In cases where new land is opened up, this leads to deforestation.

Figure 3: Illustration of nexus links – Scenario 2

3.2 Water–Energy (Hydropower)

The most extensively studied nexus link in Zambia is the relationship between energy and water in the context of hydropower generation, which is central to the country's energy supply. Key studies, including those by Yamba *et al.* (2011), Spalding-Fecher *et al.* (2017), Kaonga (2020), and Payet-Burin (2021), examine the interplay between climate, water, and hydropower energy. The studies used simulation-based methods to assess the effects of climate change on water flows and energy production, finding different climate change scenarios would have substantially different impacts on power generation.

A review by ACF and IFPRI (2023) summarised the evidence on regional trends. Climate change is expected to lead to increased average temperatures, a decline in rainfall, particularly in the southern and western regions, and a slight increase in water availability in the northern areas. This will result in greater rainfall variability, leading to more frequent droughts and floods. The overall decrease in water availability at the national level will adversely impact the Zambezi, Kafue, and Luangwa River Basins, potentially leading to increased power cuts in Zambia as river basins dry up. There are increasing risks to hydropower availability, especially in the Zambezi River Basin, threatening energy security and economic stability.

While the risks of climate change to hydropower are widely recognised, there is still uncertainty about the degree of impact, especially concerning long-term reductions in water flow versus seasonal fluctuations. This uncertainty makes it challenging for policymakers and stakeholders to plan and develop infrastructure effectively.

Current narratives and measures are prioritising development of alternative renewable energy technologies. For example, the Integrated Resource Plan (IRP) (GRZ, 2023a)

projects a decline of 7.5% in hydropower output over the plan period (2020–2050) in the Zambezi River basin. This change is attributed to both intensified climate induced droughts and continued decrease in annual precipitation, resulting in water scarcity for energy generation. Despite these challenges, the IRP maintains a projection in which future national electricity supply remains predominantly hydro-based. The IRP proposes continued or increased reliance on hydropower by shifting the hydropower development focus from the Zambezi River basin to the Congo River basin, which is anticipated to have more stable hydrology over future decades (GRZ, 2023a).

Emerging research gaps:

- Updated projections of water availability across Zambia under future climate change scenarios. These should include high temporal and spatial resolution and thorough uncertainty analysis, in order to provide the insights required for the development of robust energy strategy.
- Studies examining options for diversifying the electricity system to reduce reliance on hydropower, to ensure reliable energy supply to meet future demands.
- Studies examining how careful reservoir management could increase resilience to droughts and floods, for example investigating whether capacity could be managed to provide backup in the event of floods or to absorb flash floods.

3.3 Water–Energy (Other)

While the literature mainly focuses on impacts of climate change on hydropower generation (described in Section 3.1), several other links between the water and energy systems are also touched upon.

For example, Gonzalez Sanchez *et al.* (2020), analysed how the use of large hydropower dams affects water resources as evapotranspiration from the surface of reservoirs reduces water surrounding ecosystems and other uses, challenging both energy security and wider water management, especially in water-scarce areas. Efficient reservoir management and alternative energy options are needed to minimise these losses.

While water shortages affect hydropower generation, this also has knock-on impacts: Ahmed *et al.* (2020) analysed the increased reliance on costly, emission-heavy alternatives like diesel generators during times of droughts. As well as the power shortages disrupting economic activities and societal well-being, the increased use of diesel generators during these periods was found to raise GHG emissions.

Fuelwood extraction for cooking and heating in rural areas also has implications for water resources. Unsustainable wood extraction contributes to deforestation, land degradation,

and reduced groundwater recharge. These challenges highlight the need for sustainable energy practices to minimise negative effects on water availability (Gonzalez Sanchez *et al.*, 2020).

3.4 Land–Water–Energy (Irrigation)

Irrigation is a key focus in Zambia, due to the increasing impacts of climate change on rain-fed agriculture. Attention usually focuses on the impact of rainy season variability and droughts. Destruction of crops by floods could also increase reliance on irrigation to increase production in other areas to make up for shortfalls. Effective irrigation depends on water availability, which is increasingly impacted by climate change and competing demands. Plans are increasingly betting on greater use of irrigation for maintaining and increasing crop yields (GRZ, 2022a). The resilience of these plans, considering climate change impacts, competing demands for water, and energy requirements, along with the potential implications for optimal agricultural practices and potential expansion of agricultural land, requires careful consideration.

Estimates of current irrigation water abstraction across four sub-basins show significant variability, with the highest abstraction in the Lunsemfwa catchment (Tshenyego *et al.*, 2019). Using methods such as the FAO Penman-Monteith equation for calculating reference evapotranspiration (Tshenyego *et al.*, 2019), as well as statistical downscaling and a water balance model (Hamududu and Ngoma, 2020), research indicates that the potential for irrigation expansion varies across sub-basins due to differences in water availability, local hydrological conditions, infrastructure, and agricultural practices.

Studies show rural electrification has enabled the widespread use of solar-powered electric irrigation pumps, boosting agricultural productivity and food security. However, in some regions, this increased irrigation puts additional pressure on already limited local water sources, creating a challenge in balancing food production with sustainable water management (Falchetta *et al.*, 2023). Alternative approaches like soil management, drought-resistant crops, and agroecological farming may offer more sustainable, cost-effective solutions for improving yields (Vinca *et al.*, 2023). Sustainable growth of irrigation requires balancing competing water demands through the adoption of efficient irrigation technologies and resource management strategies (Tshenyego *et al.*, 2019; Hamududu and Ngoma, 2020).

Emerging research gaps:

- Analysis of current irrigation practices through surveys and modelling.
- Projections of water availability for irrigation under scenarios of future climate change, leading to analysis of the potential to increase irrigation.

- Focus on opportunities for the expanded use of efficient irrigation technologies supported by sustainable rural energy solutions. Integrating weather forecasts with water management systems could help optimise irrigation schedules, reducing water use during drought periods (water), minimising energy consumption for water pumping (energy), and improving crop yields (land).
- Integrated water and energy analysis is needed to inform sustainable irrigation strategies, which are in turn needed to enhance land productivity and help farmers adapt to climate change. Overall, this approach will foster sustainable and resilient agricultural practices and strengthen rural livelihoods.

3.5 Land–Water–Energy (Irrigation & hydropower)

While the studies described above generally consider irrigation and hydropower separately, others recognise that the potential to increase hydropower generation capacity and irrigation may well depend on integrated water management strategies and infrastructure development.

A key study examining this important link was developed by Spalding-Fecher *et al.* (2016), which assessed the combined effects of climate change and irrigation demand on hydropower potential in the Zambezi River basin, with the Water Evaluation and Planning (WEAP) scenario model. The study found that the generation potential of major hydropower plants is at risk, with climate change posing the greatest threat, while increased irrigation demand further exacerbates downstream impacts in Mozambique. This raises important questions about water allocation and governance between sectors but also between countries, necessitating collaborative solutions.

It is also important to consider how varying levels of demand and supply for energy and water might combine to impact the financial viability of individual infrastructure projects. To this end, Payet-Burin (2021) developed the WHAT-IF tool, which employs a hydro-economic optimisation framework. With representation of the water, power, and agriculture systems, WHAT-IF models predictive control to simulate infrastructure operations under uncertain future energy and water demands, and uncertain water levels driven by climate change. The research showed that while mean annual flow in the Zambezi is highly uncertain, rising power demands could enhance the financial feasibility of several hydro projects.

Emerging research gaps:

- Regional impacts of hydropower variability on interconnected grids, in particular the Southern African Power Pool (SAPP). This is crucial for evaluating how shifts

in hydropower production – driven by climate change and fluctuating water availability – can affect the stability and reliability of the energy grid.

- Analysis of the potential trade-offs between energy production and irrigation in the context of climate uncertainty is needed for an increased understanding of how to allocate limited water resources in times of shortages.
- Studies assessing the need for water reservoir management, in order that multiple demands for water (eg hydropower, farming, fisheries) can be met as well as possible, accounting for impacts of climate change.

3.6 Land–Water (Other)

The impact of land-use practices on water resources and hydropower generation is a significant concern in several regions, as highlighted by Ahialely *et al.* (2023). In Zambia, a detailed study of the Chongwe River Catchment (Tena *et al.*, 2019) revealed that increased built-up areas, irrigated agriculture, and rainfed farms, ranch, and grassland had led to a decrease in forest land and waterbodies, with negative consequences for the local hydrological system; the natural flow of water has been badly disrupted and the broader ecological balance has suffered.

Anthropogenic influences on water *quality* have also been documented by Winton *et al.* (2021). This study, which used water sampling and regression analysis with land use and water data, found the major rivers (Zambezi and Kafue) are mainly very clean. However, there are some hotspots where agriculture, urbanisation, and hydropower development are causing degradation of water quality. Notably, these areas suffer from thermal changes, hypoxia, and loss of suspended sediment below dams. Smaller tributaries with a relatively large anthropogenic landcover footprint in their catchments show signs of pollution in the form of higher concentrations of nutrients and dissolved ions. As agricultural intensification, urbanisation, and future hydropower development continue to accelerate in the basin, the number and extent of these hotspots of water quality degradation will grow in response.

The impacts of climate change on crop production are profound and multifaceted, mainly due to water changes, as demonstrated in the studies by Hunter *et al.* (2020), ACF and IFPRI (2023), and Matchaya *et al.* (2022). Increased temperatures and decreased or delayed rainfall are expected to reduce crop production by decreasing the area suitable for cultivation and lowering the productivity of current farming regions, especially in southern and western regions. There may be some new agricultural opportunities in the northern regions due to increased water availability; however, waterlogging and floods will also become more prevalent. Negative impacts on livestock are anticipated.

Emerging research gaps:

- A greater focus is needed on the impacts of deforestation on freshwater and groundwater resources, which remain largely underexplored.
- Methods to assist farmers rapidly increase their resilience to droughts and floods through uptake and sustained practice of conservation farming, climate-smart farming, and agroforestry. Long term, these practices should improve land productivity, lead to water resources being managed more efficiently, and increase agricultural resilience to climate variability.
- Expert stakeholder engagement to establish shared understanding of alternative approaches to farming transitions, followed by modelling to assess land, energy, and water implications.
- Strategies for optimising the management of water resources at basin-level to support both hydropower and competing uses like agriculture and industry. Balancing these demands and examining the broader impacts of hydropower on water quality and ecosystems are crucial.

3.7 Land–Energy

Land is a key input in the energy sector. The impact of charcoal production on forestry varies significantly depending on geographic location and the interplay with concurrent land-use activities. Evidence suggests that sustainably managed resources could potentially meet current and future demand (Drigo, 2016) However, degradation and deforestation appear to result where the rate of biomass removal exceeds the rate of regeneration, where the style of tree cutting prevents regeneration, where fire risk is increased, and where cleared areas are used for agriculture (Moombe *et al.*, 2020; Sedano *et al.*, 2022).

Climate change also affects charcoal consumption and therefore impacts forests. Typically, many urban households in Zambia employ fuel stacking; while 14.2% of urban households use electricity solely for cooking, a larger portion (33.6%) combine charcoal with electricity (Tembo *et al.*, 2015). In the face of recurring electricity deficits and subsequent load management measures (in 2007, 2015, 2019, and 2024, largely driven by climate-induced declines in water availability that affect electricity generation) the typical fuel stacking matrix has been distorted with more urban households switching to charcoal. The increased demand for charcoal is expected to place greater pressure on forest biomass resources, contributing to degradation and deforestation in critical hotspot areas (Moombe *et al.*, 2020; Sedano *et al.*, 2022).

A key component of government strategy to improve energy security and reduce import costs is to increase the use of bioethanol and biodiesel as transport fuels (GRZ, 2022a). The Bioenergy Food Security report (GRZ-FAO, 2020) estimates the resource potential for energy crops based on yield improvements, assuming no increase in land requirements, with solid biomass resources sourced from crop, livestock, and forestry residues. Increased crop yields could enable the achievement of bioethanol blending targets without necessitating land expansion. However, the practicality and likelihood of achieving these yield improvements is uncertain. If they are not achieved, if farmers choose to replace food production with energy crops, or if farmers expand their crop land further in response to a new market, there could be negative impacts on food security at household, regional, and national levels, or increased deforestation.

As the transition to renewable electricity technologies intensifies, the demand for land resources to develop energy infrastructure is expected to significantly increase. The more solar energy technology is deployed to build energy resilience against climate change, the more the land must be made available. The IRP report warns that poorly planned and located renewable energy projects may threaten Zambia's biodiversity and contribute to local conflicts, impeding progress in grid transformation and climate change mitigation such as forest restorations to sink carbon (GRZ, 2023a).

Emerging research gaps:

- Dynamics of forest regeneration and agricultural activities in areas cleared for charcoal production, as well as the land-use changes that may occur due to bioenergy production under different agricultural scenarios.
- Potential for sustainable charcoal production methods and viable alternatives to mitigate environmental impacts.
- Energy requirements of agricultural systems, and how improved energy access (electricity plus other improved fuels) could strengthen smallholder farming livelihoods. Examining the interactions between energy access and land-based activities will help ensure that energy solutions promote sustainable land-use and agricultural practices.
- Potential for crop yield improvements with climate resilient techniques, including the integration of energy crop production with food systems. Dynamics of farmers' decision-making around production of food and energy crops when new markets emerge, so that interventions can be designed to support resilient livelihoods and mitigate risks of deforestation.

3.8 Whole nexus

Few studies were identified which consider more than one cross-sector nexus link. One recent study by Nyoni (2024) uses the CLEWs modelling framework to examine the impact of climate change on Zambia's hydro generation, energy and water consumption, crop production and other land-use. The study examines how these impacts are interconnected with rapid urbanisation and population growth.

Several scenarios are evaluated with the model including those illustrating Business As Usual, No Adaptation, and Climate-Adjusted Infrastructure. These demonstrate how increased diversification of energy technologies (i.e. developing solar PV, geothermal and nuclear power) could enhance the country's resilience to climate change and as well as reducing emissions. Additionally, the study explores the potential of biofuels within Zambia's energy strategy, finding that, while using biofuels from maize, cassava, and sugarcane could reduce GHG emissions, increasing agricultural demands could entail trade-offs by straining Zambia's water and land resources, requiring careful management to prevent worsening food and water insecurity. The study concludes that policy coherence across Zambia's energy, water, and food systems is crucial for climate resilience and long-term socio-economic stability. By adopting a diversified, sustainable energy mix, improving water management, and integrating resilient agricultural practices, Zambia can mitigate climate change impacts and progress towards its Vision 2030 goals.

Further development and application of the CLEWs modelling framework could enable a more holistic analysis of links such as the interplay between Zambia's energy sector, water resources, food production, and climate change impacts, helping to inform policies that promote sustainable development, resilience to droughts and floods, and the efficient use of natural resources

4 How Zambian policy addresses nexus issues

4.1 Policy coherence

Policies that are most directly important for the land, energy, and water sectors were selected for review, along with those targeted to address climate change and key cross-sector policy documents (**Figure 4**). Initially, 9 policies were reviewed, then the set was expanded to 12 following the stakeholder workshop based on participants' feedback. Participants also recommended the inclusion of the Wetlands policy, National Agriculture policy, National Policy on the Environment, and the Transport Policy but these were deemed out of scope due to time limitations for the study.

Full details of the policy coherence analysis are provided in Annex 2. Figure 4 summarises the extent to which the nexus links described in the literature are reflected in the relevant policies. The colours are assigned to each policy-system intersection as follows: green denotes that relevant nexus links are fully integrated with elaborative measures or targets for actions; orange indicates that relevant nexus links are described but without clear measures or targets for action; red indicates that the relevant nexus links are described but with misaligned or unmatched measures or targets for actions; and white denotes that relevant nexus links are not described.

Policy	Climate	Land	Energy	Water
National Water Policy (GRZ, 2010)	Green	Red	Yellow	Green
National Policy on Climate Change (GRZ, 2016)	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Green
National Energy Policy (GRZ, 2019)	Red	Yellow	Green	Yellow
National Lands Policy (GRZ, 2021a)	Green	Green	White	Red
Eighth National Development Plan (GRZ, 2022a)	Green	Green	Green	Green
Nationally Determined Contribution (GRZ, 2021b)	Green	Green	Green	Green
National Adaptation Plan (GRZ, 2023b)	Green	Green	Red	Green
Integrated Resource Plan for the Power Sector (GRZ, 2023a)	Green	Yellow	Green	Green
National Green Growth Strategy (GRZ, 2024a)	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
National Mineral Resources Development Policy (GRZ, 2022b)	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
National Forestry Policy (GRZ, 2014)	Green	Green	Yellow	Green
National Infrastructure Policy (GRZ, 2023c)	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Green

Figure 4: Representation of cross-sector links in policy documents

The review revealed a significant level of integration of either one or all CLEWs thematic areas in both the sector-specific and cross-sector documents; however, there are notable gaps. On the surface, sector-specific policies recognise most of the basic interlinkages and some level of interplay between components of the CLEWs nexus. However, a detailed review shows that each sector policy is framed to specifically drive, guide, and prioritise the exploitation and management of the resources within its own domain, leaving some nexus issues under-represented, such as how to manage water resources for their multiple uses across sectors in a changing climate (see **Table 1**).

Each policy recognises relevant impacts of climate change; all warn that climate induced droughts and reduced rains will lead to water scarcity. Except for the National Lands Policy, there is a strong emphasis across the documents on energy transition to renewables to address carbon emissions and achieve energy resilience in the face of

climate change. The Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) has set measures and targets for renewable energy uptake from 3% to 10% by 2030 while the National Energy Policy only highlights measures without targets and a timeframe. The NDC is also the only policy document that highlights specific measures and targets to reduce GHG emissions in respective sectors, but these measures and targets are not reflected in the sector-specific documents.

The cross-sector policy documents such as the National Green Growth Strategy, the Eighth National Development Plan (8th NDP), and the NDC exhibit a mirror image of sector policies but also reflect a more detailed level of CLEWs nexus interplay in the outlined objectives, measures and expected outcomes.

See more detail in Annex 2 and notable limitations described in Section 4.2.

4.2 Policy gaps

Several important gaps in the policies' content were identified regarding the degree to which they account for or address nexus issues. These range from misalignment of goals, lack of clarity, and, in some instances, a complete absence of specific measures or targets for actions that literature suggests are required (**Table 1**).

Table 1: Policy gaps

Policy	Gaps
National Water Policy (GRZ, 2010)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Underscores the need to assess and monitor the potential impact of climate change on ecosystems, that is forests and wetlands, but leaves out the impact of land-use changes such as increasing land for agriculture, energy infrastructure, and settlements.
National Policy on Climate Change (GRZ, 2016)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Does not reflect the latest understanding of current and future climate change impacts, as outlined in the latest national documents such as Green Growth Strategy.• Is not aligned with the latest energy policy: For example, the policy cites the Energy Regulation Act of 2003 to address energy-related issues; yet the act in question was repealed and replaced by latest energy regulation Act 12 of 2019.
National Energy Policy (GRZ, 2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Does not include measures to reconfigure the existing hydropower facilities to optimise energy generation in the face of declining water resources.• Does not mention future coal energy projects and their implications for GHG emissions.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promotes biofuels and other renewables in the national fuel mix without linking them to land resource availability and potential GHG emissions that come with bioenergy crop production. This presents a significant risk of undercounting or double counting of emissions. In addition, neither National Energy Policy nor National Agricultural Policy specify the type of crops to be used as feedstocks for production of biofuels.
National Lands Policy (GRZ, 2021a)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Does not consider the land requirements or implications of energy provision in its objectives, measures, or targets for actions.
National Adaptation Plan (GRZ, 2023b)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The NAP itself identifies capacity gaps for planning, coordination, and implementation of adaptation actions (in Leadership; Information, Data and Analysis; Resource Mobilisation; Knowledge Management; Implementation and management; Monitoring, Learning and Accountability; Research and Technical Capacities; Social and Cultural; and Multi-Stakeholder Dialogue Processes). As these are addressed, focus should be placed on coordination between sectors in order to enhance a holistic CLEWs nexus approach.
National Green Growth Strategy (GRZ, 2024a)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is unclear whether climate-smart agriculture approaches are exclusively designated for existing cropland to prevent further expansion, intended to support continued expansion, or aimed at addressing both actions simultaneously. The policy includes measures to increase the share of renewable energy in the power generation mix, but none that speak to improving the climate resilience of existing hydropower generation. Recognises the need for a water–energy–food–ecosystems nexus approach. However, the analyses are not integrated, and a management framework is lacking.

4.3 Implementation

Adelphi (2023), which examined lessons learned from the “Nexus Regional Dialogues Programme” highlighted that governance structures often lack the required vertical and horizontal coordination to effectively institutionalise nexus approaches and ensure trade-offs and synergies are addressed at local level. This results in sector-specific policies and regulatory frameworks that impede a more integrated, cross-sectoral approach.

Like Adelphi (2023), Zambian workshop participants emphasised that limited capacity and unequal power between ministries and other sectoral actors can result in a lack of cooperation and trust, complicating efforts to implement a nexus approach for sustainable development. Challenges include the absence of a joint strategy among institutions, difficulties in harmonising sectoral regulations, and the lack of shared agreement on the goals among the different stakeholders.

Coordination structures, such as technical working groups, can serve as entry points for a nexus approach. For example, the Zambian government has implemented a technical working group, the National Charcoal Taskforce which is co-chaired by the Ministry of Energy and the Ministry of Green Economy and Environment through the Forest Department, with membership comprising stakeholders from ministries, academia, private sector, charcoal value-chain members such as the Producer Associations, and the security wings (eg The Zambia Police Service). This has the aim of accounting for climate–energy–land nexus issues. For effectiveness, this kind of structure requires political legitimacy and clear high-level mandates for cooperation, which are sometimes lacking in practice.

Sector policies are supported by specific legal instruments otherwise known as Acts of Parliament to guide and regulate the outlined activities. Sector-specific policies and Acts that do not consider nexus issues create challenges when a resource has overlapping uses and stands as a key input in the other sectors. Workshop participants highlighted some examples of this issue, as described below.

The first case relates to land policy. Land allocation and administration for diverse land uses is a top priority for the Ministry of Lands and Natural Resources but the mandate to track and monitor compliance issues and to address environmental impacts of land-use activities falls under the authority of interlinked sector policies. For instance, the Ministry of Lands and Natural Resources, in collaboration with Local Authorities under local government will invoke Lands Act 184, the Urban and Regional Planning Act of 2015, to prepare district spatial plans and land-use plans and to allocate land rights. However, the responsibility to increase awareness on land ownership and land management in communities is assigned to the Ministry of Community Development and Social Services.

For environment and climate issues associated with land use, the responsibility shifts to the Zambia Environmental Management Agency (ZEMA) and the Meteorology Department (MET) which have separate policies and legal instruments to guide their actions. Typically, ZEMA will invoke an Environment Management Act 12 of 2011 to enforce environmental compliance but, currently, neither MET nor the Green Economy and Climate Change Department (both of which are under the Ministry of Green Economy

and Environment) has a legal instrument to guide how climate change issues associated with land use must be addressed. Overall, this creates gaps and clashes in the implementation of environmental and climate interventions on land resources. Furthermore, each sector may be grappling with capacity constraints, such as financial resources, which increase the challenges associated with coordinating widely and enforcing compliance outside of their direct domain. This results in weak, casual or a complete lack of land–climate nexus in practice.

In the case of the National Water Policy, its implementation is subject to the Water Act Cap 198 and the Water Resources Management Act of 2011, which aim to ensure that the drive to optimally harness, efficiently extract, and sustainably utilise water resources for various socio-economic developmental activities is legally guided.

While land resources and vegetation adjacent to water bodies (up to 50m radius) falls under the jurisdiction of Ministry of Water Development and Sanitation, biodiversity and land resources outside the water body catchment are the responsibility of other sectors such forestry and agriculture, where land-use has the potential to influence micro-climatic conditions (precipitation, temperatures, etc) that are tied to water availability and sustainability. Within 50 metres of water bodies, land, vegetation, and water quality monitoring is the preserve of ZEMA. In such cases, coherence of policy and implementation of water protection and sustainability measures becomes difficult to collectively attain due to inherent constraints and conflict of interests compounding respective sectors linked to water resources.

Similar policy issues relevant to the land–energy–water nexus are also typical realities in the energy sector, mining sector etc. For instance, the standing forest biomass resources are under the jurisdiction of the Forest Department, responsible for managing the extraction and production of wood fuel (wood or charcoal). Conversely, managing the use of both forest biomass and crop/animal biomass fuels is the sole responsibility assigned to Ministry of Energy.

Finally, the review found that not all national policy documents have legal instruments to drive nexus objectives, measures, and targets. Key gaps were identified in the instruments required to drive the NDC. While the NDC is inspired by international decisions 1/CP.19, 1/CP.20, and 1/CP.21 of the Conference of Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), compliance to the commitment is voluntary and not legally binding, and it is therefore difficult to fully implement measures and targets due to the lack of a domestic legal instrument. The Climate Bill, which is currently in parliament, may well address the legal and implementation gaps synonymous with all the national policy documents.

A clear example of these challenges can be seen in the charcoal sector in Zambia. As noted by Kaywala (2020), while the Forests Act, Energy Regulation Act, National Energy Policy, and National Forestry Policy govern the sector, the fragmented governance approach leads to a focus on certain segments of the charcoal value chain while leaving others largely unregulated. The informal nature of the value chain further complicates enforcement, preventing the government from regulating the sector effectively and contributing to the overexploitation of forest resources by end users. This illustrates the broader issues of sectoral fragmentation and the need for integrated, coordinated governance to achieve sustainable outcomes. Efforts to coordinate the sector are currently in progress through the establishment of the National Charcoal Taskforce, which includes stakeholders from the Forest Department, security agencies, Ministry of Energy, private sector, academia, and others.

5 Recommendations

5.1 Research priorities

During the workshop, participants engaged in discussions to identify key research needs related to the CLEWs nexus. Drawing on those discussions, along with the analysis of the literature, the following research priorities are highlighted by system linkages:

- Literature, policy frameworks, and workshop participants all emphasise the critical need for diversification in the energy mix. Particularly important issues surround the implications of alternative energy sources for land. For example: i) What will be the impact of promoting alternative energy sources, such as biofuels, on food production and land use, at household, regional, and national level, and how can any social and environmental risks be mitigated? ii) What would be the implications for forests and livelihoods of changes/reduction in charcoal production? iii) To create energy strategies that are both sustainable and equitable, increased understanding is needed of the behaviour of farmers and charcoal producers, along with the potential for effective interventions to mitigate risks.
- Research is needed to determine the best ways to manage water resources under a changing climate. What are potentially the best ways to increase irrigation, with large and small-scale technologies, given competing demands for water for hydropower, residential, commercial, and industrial uses?
- Other questions concern nexus issues related to changes in agriculture. These include i) What are the effects of transitioning from small-scale to commercial farming on water and energy requirements? ii) How can climate smart and conservation agriculture approaches be scaled up to reliably achieve high yields

with efficient water resources management and improved soil health? iii) What are the impacts of the Chitemene system (shifting cultivation) on land and water?

- A broader CLEWs nexus approach to research is essential for developing a sustainable, reliable energy system for Zambia. Note, this is emerging, through collaboration between various Zambian researchers, along with the CCG and RE-INTEGRATE programmes and with United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UN DESA). Research should explore the potential role of clean energy beyond hydropower, such as solar and geothermal energy, accounting for land implications, as well as the potential to expand hydropower in northern regions to reduce pressure on water resources. Solar-powered irrigation systems should also be considered to enhance agricultural productivity while conserving water and energy. In addition, improving groundwater management, promoting water conservation at various levels, and addressing water resource degradation are critical steps. Development of reservoir management strategies should be prioritised, accounting for improved resilience in the case of increasing droughts and floods, and also the allocation of water to meet multiple demands such as hydropower, agriculture, and fisheries. Adopting an integrated, holistic nexus approach is essential for ensuring resilience in the face of climate change impacts and increased competition for resources.
- As well as assessing the technical aspects of climate change impacts, more research is needed to understand how economic and societal drivers exacerbate these vulnerabilities within Zambia, and how adaptation measures should be directed and funded.
- To address the policy issues highlighted, tools should be developed to assess the effectiveness of existing policies and identify areas for improvement (Adelphi, 2023). Stakeholder engagement with policymakers, industry experts, and community leaders could be used to improve understanding and development of strategies to address the challenges of implementing cross-sector policies, particularly at the national and regional levels.

5.2 Policy recommendations

The policy review highlighted the need to address key points related to policy coherence and implementation challenges, including the alignment of legal instruments between ministries.

Four recommendations, directed at national policymakers, were prioritised by workshop participants:

- Focus on developing diversified energy sources (beyond the focus on large-scale hydropower concentrated in the south of the country), along with efficient irrigation technologies and integrated energy and water management strategies, in order to support increased resilience and productivity in the energy and agriculture systems.
- Study how funding for implementation of activities is distributed across all the sectors in Zambia, addressing imbalances and ensuring there is provision for, or even prioritisation of, cross-sector initiatives.
- Develop ways to involve stakeholders from different policy areas more effectively in decision-making by creating better feedback systems and inclusive approaches to developing policies.
- Examine how the role of independent bodies can be developed in order to help maintain long-term policy stability and coordination across different sectors through changes in government.

Further recommendations are inspired from the “lessons learned” study (Adelphi, 2023), which provides stakeholder-specific recommendations to improve water–energy–food (WEF) nexus projects. For each, the relevance for Zambia is explained.

Private and Public Sector:

1. *Develop a Clear Business Case: Demonstrate the benefits, costs, and return on investment (ROI) of WEF Nexus projects.* A good example of this was observed in June 2023, when the Southern African Development Community (SADC), in collaboration with Zambia’s Ministries of Energy and Agriculture, handed the Katapazi WEF Nexus Demonstration Project to the community in Katapazi, Kazungula District. The project includes a solar-powered drip irrigation system covering 4 hectares, benefiting over 800 people, along with a mobile charging port for farmers. Local farmers received training in system maintenance, agricultural practices, marketing, and gender-transformative approaches to ensure sustainable use. The area is highly vulnerable to climate change, facing extreme weather events which have negatively impacted food production and livestock. The project’s provision of decentralised clean energy and water is expected to help mitigate these climate impacts and contribute to achieving SDGs 2 (Zero Hunger), 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation), and 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) (GWP, 2023). It will be essential to monitor the long-term impacts of this WEF project (and others) to strengthen the evidence base and identify effective strategies for achieving success in future nexus projects.

2. *Explore Alternative Financing: Use impact investment, green bonds, and crowdfunding to secure funding.* Zambia has made considerable progress in introducing alternative financing models, such as green bonds and climate financing. In 2023, the country made history by issuing its first green bond, valued at US\$ 53.5 million, with the aim of increasing the share of renewable energy in its national grid. This achievement was made possible by the Biodiversity Finance Initiative, which helped establish the regulatory framework for green bond issuance (BIOFIN, 2024).

Additionally, in December 2024, the Green Economy and Climate Change Bill passed its second reading and was approved by Parliament. A key objective of the bill is to establish the Climate Change Fund (GRZ, 2024b). To further build on these advancements, Zambia can encourage private sector involvement by offering incentives, such as those currently provided to actors in the renewable energy sector and climate projects (eg Green Climate Funds), and expand public–private partnerships (PPPs) to scale up sustainable initiatives. Strengthening monitoring and reporting systems for transparency, along with refining climate policies and frameworks, will ensure effective green investments and support the successful implementation of the Climate Change Fund, once the Climate Change Bill is enacted. Furthermore, empowering local communities through education on climate change and the sustainable use of resources, beyond just energy, will help reduce reliance on a single energy source and ensure inclusive benefits from climate initiatives.

3. *Use Data to Show Impact: Collect and analyse data to highlight economic, social, and environmental benefits.* Data is critical for demonstrating and communicating the impact of WEF Nexus projects. For example, the Eastern Province Jurisdictional Sustainable Landscape Program (EP-JSLP) is a long-term Results-Based Climate Finance (RBCF) initiative that emphasises the importance of sustainable landscape management. Payments for RBCF projects are made upon the submission and verification of results, which are impact data. In addition, it would be advisable to develop a systematic framework with clear metrics, standardised methods, and periodic reporting to collect, verify, and analyse WEF Nexus project impacts, incorporating independent verification to support results-based payments and build stakeholder confidence.
4. *Water–Energy–Land: Focus on aligning water, energy, and land-use policies under a combined nexus framework.* This includes developing tools to assess

policy effectiveness and identifying gaps for improvement. Additionally, it is worth exploring strategies to address implementation challenges, especially for cross-sector policies at national and regional levels.

Local, National, and Regional Stakeholders:

1. *Integrate into Policy: Incorporate the WEF Nexus into local, national, and regional policies for strategic guidance.* The Katapazi WEF Nexus Demonstration Project in Kazungula District serves as an example of the WEF nexus approach being incorporated at the local level (GWP, 2023). Multi-level policy development is needed to in order to strategically support other examples across the country.
2. *Promote Collaboration: Create institutional mechanisms to encourage coordination among sectoral actors.* This can be fostered through the existing coordination bodies and mechanisms managed by the Ministry of Green Economy and Environment to identify and address shared challenges.

Academic Institutions and Research:

1. *Include in Curriculum: Add the Nexus topic to university courses and professional training.* The nexus approach is gaining traction in sub-Saharan Africa through regional initiatives (eg SADC) and local (eg Global Water Partnership) projects. To advance this further, training, knowledge-sharing, and research support are essential for stakeholders to develop the necessary skills and collaborate across sectors. The ongoing efforts through the UN DESA and CCG programme are also helping to facilitate knowledge sharing among stakeholders in Zambia. Methods for analysing technical and governance nexus issues should be built into university curricula, in order to embed the approaches into long-term decision-making.
2. *Promote Innovation: Encourage technological and management innovations for integrated resource management.* Academia and research institutions can support WEF Nexus innovation by conducting context-specific research, offering interdisciplinary training, collaborating with stakeholders to pilot solutions, disseminating findings, and securing funding for innovative resource management projects. An example is the Future Climate for Africa (FCFA) five-year research and development programme(FCFA), which aimed to generate a body of scientific evidence on climate change to effectively support long-term planning and climate-resilient development on the African continent. Taking steps to ensure that climate

projections could be integrated into decision-making, it developed the evidence base for delivering climate services in Africa.

5.3 Summary

- Nexus issues are critical to Zambia due to the dependencies between systems highlighted under this review
- While a solid literature has been identified, understanding across specific nexus issues remains patchy. Further research needs have been identified to help further develop the evidence base to better understand such issues, and inform policy
- While some cross-ministry efforts on nexus issues have been identified, the policy review highlights a need for much stronger alignment between both policy documents and implementation. This can be furthered through wider engagement at the policy development level.
- Increased recognition of system interdependencies across policies should help a better coordinated response and more efficient allocation of resources to meet the underlying challenges

Annexes

- Annex 1 provides the tabulated literature review
- Annex 2 provides the detailed policy analysis

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